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Survey Synchronize on Selected English Word among Diamantinians: An Assessment

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Abstract

Invasion of English language, brought consequences not only to the lexicon but to the phonology as well. Diamantina National High School is an institution which promotes Discipline and Excellence Adaptation of selected words clusters was taken from 50 Grade 12 students. Only spectrographic behaviors of these sounds are look into. This research paper examine word clusters with both initial and medial position occurrence, except for /z/ clusters and focused on the stress, intonation and juncture. The discussion on the affixation processes will not include a frequency count on the variability of forms, and the central tendency (mean, median and mode) as made on Ramos et. al (2017). Simply the description of on how the subjects cope with the processes. There are three points addressed in this paper, in order to determine the characteristics of the suprasegmental. In pronunciation of initial clusters, the first constituent is uttered the same as the non-cluster correspondence. Thus, we will call that repair as full articulation of the first constituent. With regards with the third type clusters, two ways are employed; first, is the full articulation, and the second is the prosthesis /f/ /s/. For the resyllabication of clusters, word-medial clusters are examined in this paper. The ambisyllabicity of the cluster member lying along the boundary, if it is a plosive, split itself into the two syllables. Wherein, the closure of the lip belongs to the former syllable, while the explosion is on the succeeding syllables. If it is a continuant, like /f/ /s/, normally with an extended sound, it runs through the next syllable, until the burst of the next segment.

Keywords: Survey; Synchronize; Selected English Word; Diamantinians; Assessment.

1. Introduction

Based on the NAT result conducted by the NEAP from 2010 to 2017 LFG DNHS has recorded their language arena as decreasing and stagnating with 37%. This proved that the need in semantic and phonology enhancement and enrichment of English Subject must meet the criteria congruent to the research of Ramos (2017). This revealed that Cabatuanses specially the Diamantinians needs lot activities to undergo in reading and speech classes in their respective classes.

Invasion of English language, brought consequences not only to the lexicon but to the phonology as well. Foreign segments adapt processes solve by the speakers as they used the words in their conversation. The introduction of these non-native sequences is promoted as they apply morphological processes, such as infixation and reduplication to the borrowed word.

A spectrographic behavior (wave shape), present the repair used by the speakers, to accommodate such illegal construct in their language (Zuraw, 2017).

This research will focused Here are studies made on describing the characteristics and behavior of consonant clusters, especially in language like Tagalog, whose phonology does not have this sound sequences.

Zuraw (2007) investigated on the strategies employed by the Tagalog in dealing with these sound sequences when employed to affixation processes. She made a survey on the internet on the choice of forms of the speakers. From her elicited data, she ranked the splittability of the clusters when undergoing infixation.

Her study provided an insight to the strategies employed by the speakers in dealing with these sounds; however her data was from written account. It fails to capture the actual use/ forms of the speakers.

This part on the other hand, was addressed in Tantiangco et al (2009), as they made a survey on the infixed and reduplicated words with initial consonant clusters. The survey was done by asking the respondents to translate English sentences to Tagalog, using the targeted items as the base form of their verbs.

Generalization of the study provided an account on the actual use of initial word clusters, however lacks acoustic data to elaborate the findings.

For acoustic characteristics of clusters, Davidson and Stone (2003) presented an XRay of tongue movement when articulating clusters. In this paper, they contradicted the previous findings on the epenthesis of schwa or any vowel between consonants to repair an illegal sequence on the language's phonotactics. Rather, they post that, such "segment" is due to gestural mistiming on the coordination of the consonants.

According to Smith and Dechant (as cited by Galero-Tejero, 2004), reading is a key to success in school, to the development of out-of-school interests, to the enjoyment of leisure time and to personal and social adjustment. It helps him to adjust to his age mates, to become independent of parents and teachers, to select and prepare for an occupation and to achieve social responsibilities. This conceptual definition of reading held many years back is still true today. Reading is truly a very important skill that without it or lack of it will greatly affect an individual's adjustment in life.

1.1 Literature review / Theoretical background

However, while the development of reading skills is considered important, teaching such skills is not an easy task. Oftentimes, reading teachers are faced with insurmountable difficulties in teaching not only in such phases as decoding language symbols, word recognition but also in teaching comprehension skills.

It is then imperative that the teachers understand well the things expected of them – what they are to do, how they are going to do it, and when and with whom they are going to perform the task of teaching the reading skill.

Blas (2011) emphasized that instructional reading materials play an important role in the learning process of students particularly in reading comprehension. They promote independence and individuality to the learners. These materials should be appealing, relevant, and appropriate to the needs of the students and should facilitate learning. Teachers should use pertinent, accurate, and quality instructional reading materials to teach their lessons.

In order to determine the Laboratory on reading comprehension of the respondents, the researcher used the Program Evaluation. As defined by E. Posavac & R. Carey (2006), this is a formalized approach to studying the goals, processes, and impacts of projects, policies and programs. It can involve quantitative and/or qualitative methods of social research. Specifically, Impact Evaluation – the most common form of program evaluation was utilized since it determines (as best as possible) the effects of a particular program along some criteria.

The main instruments used in gathering data are questionnaire and reading comprehension tests particularly the Metropolitan Achievement Tests (Survey Battery) for the pre and posttests. The questionnaire seeks the profiles of the respondents. The SRA Reading Laboratory 2b, with an approximate reading- grade level ranging from 2.5 to 8.0, printed and published in the Philippines by the Abiva Publishing House, Inc., 1980, pursuant to agreement with Science Research Associates, Inc., is studied.

As cited by David Koenig (eHow Contributor), work by color-coding portions of reading materials according to the reading ability level required. It emphasizes the role of the student in directing his own learning, assessing his own skills as he works his way up through the levels. The age range runs from kindergarten age through to grade 12 and beyond. Teachers' handbooks guide planning, while students' handbooks enable them to keep a record of their own learning. The main textbooks, Power Builders, contain readings grouped according to color-coded levels.

1.2 Research questions

1. What are the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - a. Age
 - b. Hobbies
 - c. Materials Reference in Suprasegmental.
2. What are the strengths and weakness of the Suprasegmental of the students;
3. What are the central tendency of the percentage in Suprasegmental.

2. Method

Adaptation of selected words clusters was taken from 50 Grade 12 students . Only spectrographic behaviors of these sounds are look into.

This research paper examine word clusters with both initial and medial position occurrence, except for /z/ clusters and focused on the **stress, intonation** and **juncture**. The discussion on the affixation processes will not include a frequency count on the variability of forms, and the central tendency (mean, median and mode) as made on Ramos et. al (2017). Simply the description of on how the subjects cope with the processes.

This study provides an acoustic characteristic base from spectrogram of the world clusters produced by the Diamantinians speakers. Moreover, it examines the phonological constraints of the source language that influence the various forms of accommodation of these foreign segments.

2.1 Sample / Participants

Grade 12 Emerald and Diamond are the participants a total of 50 respondents in a purposive sampling technique.

2.2 Instrument(s)

In order to analyze the data gathered for this study, the researchers made use of the following statistical tools:

Percentage. This tool used to reduce the different sets or number or common frequencies of a comparative sets of number. It is employed as a form of numerical analysis. This is utilized to determine the proportion of the respondents in each category.

Formula:

$$P = \frac{f}{n} \times 100$$

Where:

P=percentage

f=frequency

n=number of respondents

100=constant variable

Likert Scale. This will be used to analyse the answered of the respondents through the questionnaire using the following interpretation Always(5), Often(4), Sometimes(3), Seldom(2), and Never(1).

OPTION	QUANTITATIVE DESCRIPTION	INTERVAL
5	Always	4.20-5.00
4	Often	3.40-4.19
3	Sometimes	2.60-3.39
2	Seldom	1.80- 2.59
1	Never	1.00-1.79

2.3 Data collection procedures

After the permission is granted, the researcher undertook the following steps:

1. Coordinate with the school principal by checking the following questions that is all about how they pronounced each word.
2. Do the floating of questionnaire to the respondents and test the word with sound check.
3. Compute, tabulate, analyse, and interpret the data gathered to arrive at the findings of the study.

2.4 Data analysis

In order to determine the 3's: Survey Synchronize on Selected English Word Among Diamantinians: An Assesment the researcher use quantitative and qualitative research. The quantitative research method emphasizes objective measurements and the statistical, mathematical, or numerical analysis of data collected through polls, questionnaires, and surveys, or by manipulating pre-existing statistical data using computational techniques.

3. Results

3.1 List of words

The words used in this study were applied and also the Likert Scale:

Interpretation	Score
Poor	0-9
Fair	10- 18
Good	19-27
Very Good	28-36
Excellent	37-45

3.2 Consultants

The effect of the entry of these foreign words Phonology is observed with fifty students (25 males and 25 females). All are native Tagalog speakers. None of them have reported speech difficulties.

3.3 Recording Procedure

There are three parts of the experiment. The first part is the 15 word reading task STRESS 15 word reading task INTONATION, 15 word reading task JUNCTURE.

3.4 Analysis

The recordings were analyzed using PRAAT 5.1.25 software (Jun-Jun Ramos and Mark Jhon R. Prestoza, Isabela State University). Segments of each constituent were identified with their spectrographic features.

1. Characteristics of consonant clusters

There are three types of clusters dealt in this paper, first type is stop + liquid (r/l), second type is stop + glide (w/y/) and the third type is the /s/+ Consonant(s).

In this section word initial clusters are examined, in particular description to the first constituent of the cluster.

2. Morphological Consequences

The respondents were asked to use the words in table 1, 2 and 3. Each word is targeted to be infixed and reduplicated. The targeted items are listed on the appendix. The summary of their resulting forms is divided into two: unbroken and broken clusters. However, in an actual speech, Zuraw noted that the difference on the resulting forms in coping to these morphological processes is not notable or often heard as similar forms by the speakers. For the unbroken clusters, similar repair with initial clusters in section 3 is observed.

Table 1: Profile of the respondents in terms of AGE

Bracketing	Percentage	Total
12-15	5	5%
16-20	40	90%
21-25	5	5%

Table 2: Profile of the respondents in terms of HOBBIES

Bracketing	Percentage	Total
Watching	10	5%
Reading	10	5%
Writing	50	50%
Listening	5	5%
Others	25	25%

Table 3: Profile of the respondents in terms of MATERIALS REFERENCE

Bracketing	Frequency	Total
Newspaper	22	22
Book	15	15
Internet	23	23
Television	30	30
Classroom Discussion	25	25
Chatting/Discourse	25	25

Table 4: Selected Words and Frequency.

	Poor	Fair	Good	Very Good	Excellent
STRESS					
1. politics – political – politician	0	8	7	5	25
2. oligarch – oligarchic – oligarchy	5	3	7	4	26
3. origin – original – originality	2	2	2	5	40
4. sedate – sedative – sedation	7	3	5	5	30
5. satire – satiric – satirical	4	4	7	10	30
6. personal – personality – personification	1	1	7	9	25
7. operate – operation – operational	4	0	3	13	25
8. oppose – opposite – opposition	5	8	0	2	25
9. oppress – oppressive – oppression	5	3	2	10	25
10. Correct – corrector – correction	4	3	10	0	28
11. person – personal – personage	0	0	0	10	40
12. profess – profession – professional	1	5	0	5	35
13. express – expressive – expression	0	8	7	2	2
14. notice – notify – noticeable	5	9	2	5	27
15. pagan – paganism – paganize	5	5	5	5	25
INTONATION					
1. Stay away from the corridor.	0	2	3	10	35
2. What are you driving at?	0	5	5	3	37
3. I don't expect it.	4	4	2	5	30
4. We're lucky.	5	3	3	5	29
5. The girls prepared some sandwiches.	3	5	7	10	30
6. Your skirt is too long.	5	3	7	5	25
7. I have to think about it.	0	0	7	13	25
8. Please send me your latest photograph.	5	8	0	2	30
9. Pia loves to go to the bookstore.	5	3	2	10	25
10. It doesn't matter.	5	1	8	2	28
11. Her birthday is on December.	0	0	5	5	40
12. The dance was enjoyed by everyone.	0	5	5	5	35
13. I don't mean it.	0	8	7	2	2
14. Aida keeps breaking her promises.	5	3	7	5	27
15. We're expecting him tonight.	5	3	7	0	30

JUNCTURE					
1. If he cries out to me, I will hear him.	5	5	5	5	30
2. To the Lord, the perverse is an abomination.	1	9	10	5	25
3. You belong to the Kingdom if you feed the hungry.	3	2	5	10	30
4. God created man in his image; in the divine image, he created him.	9	1	10	20	10
5. What is hidden in darkness, he will bring to light.	7	4	7	6	30
6. Have we not all one Father?	5	10	5	5	30
7. I will sing unto the Lord because he has dealt beautifully with me.	0	5	5	10	30
8. Where envy and strife are, there is confusion and every evil thing.	8	8	8	10	12
9. Why do you think evil in your hearts?	10	5	5	10	20
10. Let us come before him giving thanks.	5	5	5	5	30
11. Let all that you do be done in love.	0	5	5	5	35
12. If we serve others through love, we serve ourselves as well.	0	10	0	10	30
13. Pay attention when the Lord corrects you.	5	5	10	20	10
14. Continue steadfastly in prayer, watching therein with thanksgiving.	5	5	5	25	10
15. If I forgot you, may my right hand be forgotten.	0	3	7	5	35
	5	3	7	5	25

Table 4: Selected Words and Frequency.

Stress	Central Tendency	Intonation	Central Tendency	Juncture	Central Tendency
Mean	3.86	Mean	3.84	Mean	3.96
Standard Error	0.164155	Standard Error	0.154814	Standard Error	0.145574
Median	4	Median	4	Median	4
Mode	5	Mode	5	Mode	4
Standard Deviation	1.160753	Standard Deviation	1.0947	Standard Deviation	1.029365
Sample Variance	1.347347	Sample Variance	1.198367	Sample Variance	1.059592
Kurtosis	0.050305	Kurtosis	0.048003	Kurtosis	1.133738
Skewness	-0.77662	Skewness	-0.7391	Skewness	-1.08692
Range	4	Range	4	Range	4
Minimum	1	Minimum	1	Minimum	1
Maximum	5	Maximum	5	Maximum	5
Sum	193	Sum	192	Sum	198
Count	50	Count	50	Count	50
Largest(1)	5	Largest(1)	5	Largest(1)	5
Confidence Level (95.0%)	0.329882	Confidence Level (95.0%)	0.31111	Confidence Level (95.0%)	0.292542

Based on the self constructed words by the researcher, stress suprasegmentals have 3.86 and interpreted as Accepted same with the Intonation and Juncture.

Correlations			FILIPINO	ILUKO
Spearman's rho	Percentage of Suprasegmental	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.999**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	50	50
Strength and Weakness		Correlation Coefficient	.999**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	50	50
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).				

Based on the self constructed words by the researcher their strength and weakness are stress and it is highly significant at 0.01level. According to the study of Prestoza (2017) their similarity in findings stress symbols are hard more specifically their age bracket from high school is not well oriented therefore curriculum developer must give a lot of activities and drills.

4. Discussion

The administration, through the reading teachers, should strictly implement a regular Speaking Zone among the students. Proper monitoring must also be conducted by the English coordinator to ensure the utilization of the program. There must still be an integration of speaking and reading laboratory in order to develop the holistic communication skills of the learners.

To develop self –confidence in their oral communication subject they must create enhancement program such as “Speak Out”., Project Louder and Tik-Tok;. The results of this study must be coordinated to the SDO Isabela department in addition to the profile of the students which then serve as feedback to the parents on the scholastic records of their children as well as for future references. This study can be a basis for proposing a new reading program or instructional material suitable to the learning conditions of Filipino learners; A parallel study can be conducted to other schools implementing the same reading program for comparison purposes.

5. Conclusions

There are three points addressed in this paper, in order to determine the characteristics of the suprasegmental. In pronunciation of initial clusters, the first constituent is uttered the same as the non-cluster correspondence. Thus, we will call

that repair as full articulation of the first constituent. With regards with the third type clusters, two ways are employed; first, is the full articulation, and the second, is the prosthesis /f/ /s/.

For the resyllabication of clusters, word-medial clusters are examined in this paper. The ambisyllabicity of the cluster member lying along the boundary, if it is a plosive, split itself into the two syllables. Wherein, the closure of the lip belongs to the former syllable, while the explosion is on the succeeding syllables. If it is a continuant, like /f/ /s/, normally with an extended sound, it runs through the next syllable, until the burst of the next segment.

When coping with infixation and reduplication processes, clusters can be either broken or unbroken. For unbroken clusters, production of the segments is the same with that on the initial clusters in base form. On the other hand, teachers of the Senior High School must give an schematic background in this scenario.

For further studies, statistical comparison among the duration of the clusters of English word and Tagalog speakers would support the difference with the production of clusters in these languages. As well as characterization of the suprasegmental words and sentences would better describe the repairs employ by senior high school students, to verify the status of excrescent word post by Ramos et al (2004).

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